

**REALIZING THE SECRETS FOR A LONG AND HAPPY LIFE WITH
THE HELP OF THE BOOK "IKIGAI" BY HECTOR GARCIA AND
FRANCESC MIRALLES**

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ABSTRACT: This article's aim is to explain to all of you how to live correctly and how to get a joyful life expectancy. And hopefully i will write this for you that you could find your own ikigai in any branch of your entire world. If you read this article, you will be in better position than you were. If you have not found your ikigai yet, you will start searching from the space around you or if you have already found it, you will keep dealing with it.

Key words: Ikigai, japanese, life, supercentenarian, interview.

What is Ikigai ?

Ikigai is the thing that is able to give you lots of love. If you can find your ikigai, you cannot be bored at any situation with it. You always feel joy and relax from doing that chore. The more you can savour your ikigai the more you want to live in this world.

INTRODUCTION

First of all that will be appropriate if here is given the main idea about the authors of the book "Ikigai". So it has two authors who tried to share the real life of the Japanese. They said that: "Japanese people do not like retiring that's why almost of all are centenarians..."

Hector Garcia was born in Spain in 1981, has been living in Tokyo since 2004 and Francesc Miralles was born in Spain in 1968. Significantly they had an experience for the life of the Japanese with their book "Ikigai"

On the other hand Japanese people know how to get the true joyful life with their ikigai. The most famous proverb is available in Japan. It is like that - "Only staying active will make you want to live hundred years"

What is more the Japanese do not really want to retire even if they are at the age of retirement. Because they want to have joy and be active like the young.

So many interviewers had meetings with the supercentenarian Japanese people. In one of the most amazing interviews was with 116 year-old supercentenarian. She was Maria Capovilla who was born in Ecuador in 1889. She said that she was so happy and she would thank for God who kept her going. She never thought she would live so long. She: "Even after my husband's death, everything was fine. We would dance with younger people but anyways we were restrained. I had joy from dancing because my lovely song was "Maria" by Luis Alarcon. I still remember the most of the words. I like waltz and can still dance it even if I am too old to be able to dance like how I danced when I was young..."

That was her ikigai for Maria Capovilla to dance and waltz. Additionally when she was asked "What's the secret for your longevity?" She replied: "The only thing that I do is I have never eaten meat in my entire life. I attribute it to that. And also with the support of my lovely habits: dancing and waltzing."

CONCLUSION

Exercising, dieting, walking ten thousands steps, we do all this and much more to stay fit, to live long. But is that enough to live a long, and healthy life? What should we do to live a long and happy life? This book, a result of studying, and interviewing super-centenarians in the small island of Okinawa, Japan, tells us...

In clearly marked chapters, the book covers the importance of exercising, eating only up to we're 80% full, building a community, and most importantly, a sense of purpose to live a long and fulfilling life. They talk about how the super-centenarians exercise in simple movements, walk, tend their gardens. How they all look after each other in their small island community, and how they mainly eat home cooked food, getting 60% of their calories from vegetables.

Interspersed between tips to longevity are interviews with Okinawa's super-centenarians some of which are hilarious! Like when asked how they live so long, one of them replied, "I don't know, I just didn't die." And that's my takeaway from this book. No one knows how long you'll live, or whether you can live upto a hundred by following these tips. We just don't know when we'll die. So I believe it's important to focus on the quality of life. Rather than build a community so you'll probably live longer, build one so you'll engage with people every waking day you spend on this Earth. Learn something from each other, help each other! Have a purpose in life, not with the goal that it'll push you to live longer but because you'll be motivated to get out of bed every day that you're alive!

This book talks about the secrets to a long life, but to me, these are secrets to a good quality of life and frankly, they're no secrets. This is how our grandparents, and great- grandparents have lived, and we are now realizing that going back to those methods is our chance of thriving as a community- to live a happy and beautiful life!

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